

Running the WASHU Immunogenomics Workflow on Google Cloud - public version

Preamble

This tutorial demonstrates how to run the WASHU immunogenomics pipeline (immuno.wdl) on Google Cloud.

The same principles described in this tutorial should work for any of our collection of WDL files found here: <https://github.com/griffithlab/analysis-wdls>.

This workflow run will be accomplished by first setting up workflow definitions, input data and reference files, and a YAML config file on a user's local system. The user will also set up a Google Cloud environment and all the inputs will be staged to this cloud environment. Next, Cromwell will be used to execute the pipeline using the specified input and reference files, and finally, the results will be pulled back to the local system and cloud resources will be cleaned up.

Some steps are run within docker containers. It therefore requires that you can run interactive docker sessions on your system.

You will interact with the Google Cloud in several ways:

1. From your local system using command line tools, including `gcloud` and `gsutil`.
2. We will create a Google Virtual Machine (VM) and start a Cromwell service on it. You will then login to this VM and perform some commands and monitor workflow progress there. Cromwell on this VM will orchestrate the creation and use of many additional worker VMs that complete all the compute tasks of the workflow.
3. The Google Cloud Console in your web browser may be used to visualize/monitor the usage of cloud resources. In the Console, you will see the most relevant resources in the "Cloud Storage" and "Compute Engine" sections.

This version assumes that you are staging your input data files from your local system (e.g. a laptop, but could be any system really). All input files will be staged to a Google Storage Bucket. During the workflow, all results files will also be stored in this Bucket. At the end of the tutorial the final results will be copied back to your local system.

After completing the workflow, ALL resources used on the cloud can be destroyed. One possible exception to this may occur if you need custom reference files that you wish to persist for many analyses.

A brief note on command line sessions. Almost everything below will occur at the command line. It is very easy to get confused about the kind of sessions used. There are three types that will be used:

1. A terminal session on your local system (e.g. using the Terminal App on a Mac laptop)
2. Within session (1) you may launch a docker interactive session (via `docker run -it`) to use tools we have created for setting up the workflow
3. Within session (1) you may login (via `gcloud compute ssh`) to the Google Virtual Machine where Cromwell is running.

Source of instructions

This tutorial is an example of how to run a specific pipeline (immuno) on a specific example dataset (HCC1395 Tumor/normal cell line pair). The steps below are taken from the following link where you will find a more generic set of documentation that explains in detail how to run any WDL pipeline on the Google Cloud using tools created to assist this process. <https://github.com/griffithlab/cloud-workflows/tree/main/manual-workflows>

Prerequisites

- docker
- google-cloud-sdk
- git

Example data set and analysis to be performed

To demonstrate an analysis on the Google cloud we will run the WASHU immunogenomics pipeline on a publicly available set of exome and bulk RNA-seq data generated for a tumor/normal cell line pair (HCC1395 and HCC1395/BL). The HCC1395 cell line is a well known breast cancer cell line that can be purchased and is commonly used for benchmarking cancer genomics analysis and methods development. The datasets we will use here are realistic deeply sequenced exome and RNA-seq data. The immunogenomics pipeline is a very elaborate end-to-end pipeline that starts with raw data and performs data QC, germline variant calling, somatic variant calling (multiple variant callers and variant types), HLA typing, RNA expression analysis and neoantigen identification.

Setting up a Google Cloud account

In order to do analysis on the Google Cloud, you will need an account. Ideally this will be an account linked to your institution/company. Before proceeding, you should set up this account, log into it and make sure you have access to billing information: <https://console.cloud.google.com/>.

Some notes on account setup once you are logged in:

- Create a new project. In this tutorial we use project name: 'test-immuno'. When using the Google Web Console, remember to select this project in the top left corner.
- Create billing alerts! In the Google Cloud Web Console, select: Billing -> Budgets & alerts -> Create Budget. How you set up your alerts will depend on your anticipated level of use/expenditure. For example, you might set a \$500 budget and then set up alerts to be sent at 50%, 100%, 200%, ..., X% of that budget.
- Choose a name for the Google bucket that will be used for this tutorial. Note that you don't need to create it in the console because this will be handled automatically for you below. We will use the bucket name 'test-immuno-pipeline' below.

Some notes on quotas:

- If you have not been using your account for high-performance computing, it is likely that the quotas in place will cause the very large immuno.wdl workflow to fail. For example, you may not be able to use enough CPUs, IP addresses and disk space at once to get the workflow to run. If you see errors that mention quotas, or sound like fundamental network failures, check your quotas in the Google Cloud Console (IAM & Admin -> Quotas) and work with your Google account contact to increase your

quotas. If your institution has already been using Google Cloud in any serious way, this is less likely to be a problem.

Example quotas you might need to request:

- `cpus -> us-central1 -> 100`
- `preemptible_cpus -> us-central1 -> 100`
- `In-use IP addresses -> us-central1 -> 25`
- `Persistent Disk SSD (GB) -> us-central1 -> 10 TB`

Interacting with Google buckets from your local system

Note that, if needed, you can use the following docker image to access `gsutil` for exploration of your google storage: `docker(google/cloud-sdk)`. Or alternatively, you can install the Google Cloud SDK on your system. This latter approach is assumed by the following instructions.

Step-by-step instructions

Start by opening a Terminal session on your local system

Set some Google Cloud and other environment variables

The following environment variables are used merely for convenience and should be customized to produce intuitive labelling for your own analysis:

```
export GCS_PROJECT=test-immuno # REPLACE WITH YOUR PROJECT NAME
export GCS_SERVICE_ACCOUNT=cromwell-
server@$GCS_PROJECT.iam.gserviceaccount.com
export GCS_BUCKET_NAME=test-immuno-pipeline
export GCS_BUCKET_PATH=gs://test-immuno-pipeline
export SAMPLE=hcc1395
export GCS_INSTANCE_NAME=${SAMPLE}-immuno-test
export WORKING_BASE=~/Desktop/pipeline_test/gcp_wdl_test
export RAW_DATA_DIR=~/Desktop/pipeline_test/raw_data
export WORKFLOW_DEFINITION=$WORKING_BASE/git/analysis-
wlds/definitions/immuno.wdl
export LOCAL_YAML=${SAMPLE}_immuno_local-WDL.yaml
export CLOUD_YAML=${SAMPLE}_immuno_cloud-WDL.yaml
```

NOTE: You will need to manually create the Google billing project in the console before proceeding

Local setup

First create a working directory on your local system

The following directory on the local system will contain: (a) a git repository for this tutorial including an example YAML file set up to work with the test HCC1395 data, (b) git repository for the WDL workflows, including the immuno workflow, (c) git repository for tools that help provision and manage our workflow runs on the cloud, (d) raw data that we will download for this tutorial, (e) a YAML file describing the input data

and parameters for the analysis, and (f) final results file from the workflow that we will pull down from the cloud after a successful run.

```
mkdir -p $WORKING_BASE
cd $WORKING_BASE
```

Clone git repositories that have the workflows (pipelines) and scripts to help run them

The following repositories contain: this tutorial (immunoNX), the WDL workflows (analysis-wdls), and tools for running these on the cloud (cloud-workflows). Note that the command below will clone the branch of each repo that was tested and verified to work for this tutorial. If you would like to keep up with our latest updates, the release branches can be found at the respective GitHub repositories. Note that the analysis-wdls repository cloned at this step is only for record keeping. The version used by the pipeline itself depends on the cloud-workflows repository.

```
mkdir git
cd git

git clone https://github.com/griffithlab/ImmunoNX_protocol.git

git clone --branch v1.4.0 https://github.com/wustl-oncology/analysis-wdls.git

git clone --branch v1.4.8 https://github.com/wustl-oncology/cloud-workflows.git
```

Login to GCP and set the desired project

From the command line, you will need to authenticate your cloud access (using your google cloud account credentials). This generally only needs to be done once, though there is no harm to re-authenticating. The login command below will generate a custom URL to enter in your browser. Once you do this, you will be prompted to log into your Google account. If you have multiple Google accounts (e.g. one for your institution/company and a personal one) be sure to use the correct one. Once you have logged in you will be presented with a long code. Enter this at the prompt generated by the login command below. Finally, set your desired Google Project. This Project should correspond to a Google Billing account in the Google console. If you are using Google Cloud for the first time, both billing and a project should be set up before proceeding. Configuring billing alerts is also wise at this point.

```
gcloud auth login
gcloud config set project $GCS_PROJECT
gcloud config list
```

Set up cloud service account, firewall settings, and storage bucket

Run the following command and make note of the "Service Account" returned (e.g. "cromwell-server@test-immuno.iam.gserviceaccount.com"). Make sure this matches the value in `$GCS_SERVICE_ACCOUNT` (e.g. `echo $GCS_SERVICE_ACCOUNT`). If the project already exists you will see errors but as long as the Service Account is returned then everything has executed correctly.

```
cd $WORKING_BASE/git/cloud-workflows/manual-workflows/  
bash resources.sh init-project --project $GCS_PROJECT --bucket  
$GCS_BUCKET_NAME # you may have to specify ip addresses depending on  
google cloud bucket permissions
```

This step should have created two new configuration files in your current directory: `cromwell.conf` and `workflow_options.json`.

Download input data files

Download RAW data for hcc1395

```
mkdir -p $RAW_DATA_DIR/hcc1395  
cd $RAW_DATA_DIR/hcc1395  
wget https://genomedata.org/hcc1395/fastqs/all/Exome_Norm.tar  
wget https://genomedata.org/hcc1395/fastqs/all/Exome_Tumor.tar  
wget https://genomedata.org/hcc1395/fastqs/all/RNAseq_Tumor.tar  
tar -xvf Exome_Norm.tar  
tar -xvf Exome_Tumor.tar  
tar -xvf RNAseq_Tumor.tar  
rm -f Exome_Norm.tar Exome_Tumor.tar RNAseq_Tumor.tar
```

Create a copy of reference and annotation files in your Google Bucket

You may either make a set of reference files using instructions provided in the [Preparing_references.md](#) document. If you want to use our group's references, you can make a copy of a bundle of reference files from our Public ("Requestor Pays") Google Bucket to your own Google Bucket as follows:

```
gsutil -u $GCS_PROJECT ls gs://griffith-lab-workflow-inputs/  
gsutil -u $GCS_PROJECT cp -r gs://griffith-lab-workflow-  
inputs/human_GRCh38_ens105 $GCS_BUCKET_PATH/human_GRCh38_ens105  
gsutil ls $GCS_BUCKET_PATH/human_GRCh38_ens105
```

Obtain an example configuration (YAML) file on local system

Create a directory for YAML files and in that, create a YAML file that points to the location of input files on your local system. In this case, the local YAML file should point to the locations that the raw hcc1395 data was downloaded to.

```
cd $WORKING_BASE
mkdir yamls
cd yamls
```

Setup YAML files for the example run. Copy the template YAML file in this repository and rename it based on the previously described environment labels.

```
cp
$WORKING_BASE/git/ImmunoNX_protocol/example_yamls/template_immuno_local-
WDL.yaml $WORKING_BASE/yamls/
mv $WORKING_BASE/yamls/template_immuno_local-WDL.yaml
$WORKING_BASE/yamls/$LOCAL_YAML
```

Note that this YAML file has been set up to work with the HCC1395 raw data files downloaded above. You will need to update the PATHs to the FASTQ files by adding filepaths to match the locations where data was downloaded. You will also need to replace [path to reference folder] in the YAML to match the location of your newly created/copied reference directory.

If you are modifying this tutorial to work with your own data, you will need to modify the YAML lines that relate to input sequence files. For both DNA and RNA files, both FASTQ and Unaligned BAM files are supported as input. Similarly, you may have your data in one pair of files or multiple pairs of files that will be merged together. Depending on how your input data is organized the YAML entries will look slightly different.

Stage input data files to cloud bucket

The reference and annotation files should already be in your Google Bucket. However, the input FASTQ data files are still only on your local system, so we need to upload them and update our YAML file to point to their new locations on the cloud.

Start an interactive docker session capable of running the "cloudize" scripts. Note that the following docker command uses `--env` commands to pass some convenient environment variables in that were exported above. The first `-v` option is used to allow access to where the data is stored. The second `-v` is used to expose the location of the Google Cloud Credential files. You will need to update this to reflect your username. The `-it` option is used to make the session interactive and helps us drop into a `/bin/bash` session. The `mgibio/cloudize-workflow:latest` docker image has the helper scripts we need to upload files to the Google Bucket and make the new YAML file.

```
docker pull mgibio/cloudize-workflow:latest
docker run -it --env GCS_PROJECT --env GCS_BUCKET_NAME --env
GCS_BUCKET_PATH --env GCS_INSTANCE_NAME --env GCS_SERVICE_ACCOUNT --env
WORKING_BASE --env WORKFLOW_DEFINITION --env LOCAL_YAML --env CLOUD_YAML -
v $PWD:$PWD -v ~/.config/gcloud:/root/.config/gcloud mgibio/cloudize-
workflow:latest /bin/bash
```

Attempt to cloudize your workflow and inputs by running the python script in this docker image.

```
cd $WORKING_BASE/yamls
python3 /opt/scripts/cloudize-workflow.py $GCS_BUCKET_NAME
$WORKFLOW_DEFINITION $WORKING_BASE/yamls/$LOCAL_YAML --
output=$WORKING_BASE/yamls/$CLOUD_YAML
```

Note that this "cloudize" step is primarily about staging input files that you may have locally on your system that need to be copied to a google cloud bucket so that they can be accessed during your workflow run on the cloud. It therefore takes the desired Google Cloud Bucket Name as input. It also takes the appropriate Workflow Definition (WDL) pipeline file. It will perform some basic checks of the input expectations of this workflow against the input YAML configuration file you provide. The local YAML configuration file you updated above is the input for this command. This should contain all the input parameters needed by your workflow, including paths to reference, annotation and data files. If any of the file paths in your input YAML are local paths, this script will attempt to copy them into your bucket. If a file path is already specified as a Google Cloud Bucket path (e.g. gs://PATH) it will be skipped. The output of the script (the Cloud YAML), is a version of your YAML that has been updated to point to new paths for any files that were copied into the cloud bucket. This Cloud YAML will be used to launch your workflow run in the following steps.

If you get an error during this step, a common cause is that there is some disconnect between what inputs you have defined in your YAML file and what the WDL workflow definition expects. Often the error message will hint at where to look in these two files. You should also look through the Cloud YAML file at this step to ensure that all the filepaths pointing to the local data have been updated to `gs://` filepaths, and the files are uploaded to your Google Bucket. If there are filepaths that did not get updated, that may point to an incorrect filepath that needs to be corrected.

Start a Google VM that will run Cromwell and orchestrate completion of the workflow

Note that Cromwell produces a large quantity of database logging. To ensure we have enough space for a least a few runs and to localize intermediate and final results files from the workflow (which include numerous large BAMs) we will specify some extra disk space with `--boot-disk-size=250GB` (default would be 10GB). When not testing, this can probably be safely reduced to 20-40GB. Note that this argument must be listed last after the required arguments for the `start.sh` script.

```
cd $WORKING_BASE/git/cloud-workflows/manual-workflows/
bash start.sh $GCS_INSTANCE_NAME --server-account $GCS_SERVICE_ACCOUNT --
project $GCS_PROJECT --boot-disk-size=250GB

#Now exit the interactive docker session
exit
```

Log into the VM and check status

In this step we will confirm that we can log into our Cromwell VM with `gcloud compute ssh` and make sure it is ready for use.

After logging in, use `journalctl` to see if the instance start-up has completed, and cromwell launch has completed.

For details on how to recognize whether these processes have completed, refer: [here](#).

```
gcloud compute ssh $GCS_INSTANCE_NAME
journalctl -u google-startup-scripts -f
journalctl -u cromwell -f
exit
```

Localize your inputs file

First **on your local system**, copy your cloudized YAML file to the Google bucket.

```
cd $WORKING_BASE/yamls/
gsutil cp $CLOUD_YAML $GCS_BUCKET_PATH/yamls/$CLOUD_YAML
```

Now log into Google Cromwell VM instance again and copy the YAML file from the Google bucket to the VM.

```
gcloud compute ssh $GCS_INSTANCE_NAME

export GCS_BUCKET_PATH=gs://test-immuno-pipeline
export CLOUD_YAML=hcc1395_immuno_cloud-WDL.yaml

gsutil cp $GCS_BUCKET_PATH/yamls/$CLOUD_YAML .
```

Run the immuno workflow using everything setup thus far

While logged into the Google Cromwell VM instance:

```
source /shared/helpers.sh
submit_workflow /shared/analysis-wdls/definitions/immuno.wdl $CLOUD_YAML
```

Once the workflow is submitted, it will generate a unique Workflow ID that can be used to track your run's progress. While this workflow ID can be retrieved, we recommend that you make a note of this workflow ID at this stage.

Monitor progress of the workflow run:

While the job is running you can see Cromwell logs live as they occur by running this command:

```
journalctl -f -u cromwell
```

You can also check the status of an ongoing run by querying Cromwell using the workflow ID. This should give an output of 'Running', 'Failed', or 'Succeeded'.

```
export WORKFLOW_ID=<id from above>
curl http://localhost:8000/api/workflows/v1/$WORKFLOW_ID/status
```

Once a run has completed successfully, the end of the log file will display a message similar to:

```
Jul 31 16:54:00 hcc1395-immuno-test java[1739]: 2025-07-31 16:54:00
cromwell-system-akka.dispatchers.engine-dispatcher-9995 INFO -
WorkflowManagerActor: Workflow actor for 9c706ccd-4047-4f31-8927-
5f0fec558156 completed with status 'Succeeded'. The workflow will be
removed from the workflow store.
```

Save information about the workflow run itself - Timing Diagram and Outputs List

After a workflow is run, before exiting and deleting your VM, make sure that the timing diagram and the list of outputs are available so you can make use of the data outside of the cloud.

First determine your WORKFLOW_ID if it was not recorded previously. This can be done in several ways. If the run was successful it should be reported at the bottom of the cromwell log as "\$WORKFLOW_ID completed with status Succeeded". Alternatively, you can find it by the name of the directory where your run was stored in the Google bucket. Both of these approaches are illustrated here:

```
export GCS_BUCKET_PATH=gs://test-immuno-pipeline
gsutil ls $GCS_BUCKET_PATH/cromwell-executions/immuno/

journalctl -u cromwell | tail | grep "Workflow actor"
```

Now save the workflow information in your google bucket.

```
export WORKFLOW_ID=<id from above>
source /shared/helpers.sh
save_artifacts $WORKFLOW_ID
$GCS_BUCKET_PATH/workflow_artifacts/$WORKFLOW_ID
```

This command will upload the workflow's artifacts to your google bucket so they can be used after the VM is deleted. They can be found at paths:

```
$GCS_BUCKET_PATH/workflow_artifacts/$WORKFLOW_ID/timing.html  
$GCS_BUCKET_PATH/workflow_artifacts/$WORKFLOW_ID/outputs.json
```

Confirm that they were successfully transferred and logout of the Cromwell VM on GCP:

```
gsutil ls $GCS_BUCKET_PATH/workflow_artifacts/$WORKFLOW_ID  
exit
```

The file `outputs.json` will be a map of output names to their GCS locations. The `pull_outputs.py` script retrieves the output files.

Pulling the Outputs from Google Cloud Bucket back to your local system or cluster

After the work in your Google VM is completed, including `save_artifacts`, and you want to bring your results back to the cluster, leverage the `pull_outputs.py` script with the generated `outputs.json` to retrieve the files.

On your local system, with the previously defined environment variables loaded, enter a docker container with the script available:

```
export WORKFLOW_ID=<id from above>  
  
docker run -it --env WORKFLOW_ID --env GCS_BUCKET_PATH --env WORKING_BASE  
-v $PWD:$PWD -v ~/.config/gcloud:/root/.config/gcloud mgibio/cloudize-  
workflow:latest /bin/bash
```

Execute the script:

```
cd $WORKING_BASE  
mkdir final_results  
cd final_results  
  
python3 /opt/scripts/pull_outputs.py --outputs-  
file=$GCS_BUCKET_PATH/workflow_artifacts/$WORKFLOW_ID/outputs.json --  
outputs-dir=$WORKING_BASE/final_results/  
exit
```

Examine the outputs briefly:

```
cd $WORKING_BASE/final_results  
ls -l  
du -h
```

Estimate the cost of executing your workflow

On your local system, start an interactive docker session and then use the following python script to generate a cost estimate:

```
export WORKFLOW_ID=<id from above>

docker run -it --env WORKFLOW_ID --env GCS_BUCKET_PATH --env WORKING_BASE
-v $PWD:$PWD -v ~/.config/gcloud:/root/.config/gcloud mgibio/cloudize-
workflow:latest /bin/bash

cd $WORKING_BASE/git/cloud-workflows/scripts
python3 estimate_billing.py $WORKFLOW_ID
$GCS_BUCKET_PATH/workflow_artifacts/$WORKFLOW_ID/metadata/
exit
```

Once the workflow is done and results retrieved, destroy the Cromwell VM on GCP to avoid wasting resources

Use the following command to destroy the Cromwell VM.

```
gcloud compute instances delete $GCS_INSTANCE_NAME
```

You can empty the cloud bucket either in the Web Console or using commands like `gsutil rm -r $GCS_BUCKET_PATH/folder-name`.

Finally, we recommend you perform a survey of Cloud Storage and Compute Engine sections in the Google Cloud Web Console to make sure everything has been cleaned up successfully.